

A Paper on Innovation in Curriculum Design and Technology - Enabled Teaching Pedagogy

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2020

P-ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Mitra, Anupam. "A Paper on Innovation in Curriculum Design and Technology - Enabled Teaching Pedagogy." *Shanlax International Journal of Management*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2020, pp. 33–40.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3737718>

Dr. Anupam Mitra

*Professor, Department of Commerce & Management
Team Lease Skills University, Vadodara*

Abstract

Teaching pedagogy nowadays is experiencing multi-dimensional aspects, and it is shifting from the stereotype lecture-based classroom set up to more of a learner-centric environment. Institutions may implement such modern practices to walk along with the rapid changes in the learning attitude at present times. Identification of effective teaching methodologies and instructional designs based on the application of Bloom's taxonomy is transforming the teaching pedagogy with active learning. Use of technology teaching tools are in sense will fulfill the objective of designing an innovative curriculum and teaching pedagogy for better learning outcome in modern days.

Keywords: Active learning, Technology, Teaching tools, Bloom's taxonomy.

Introduction

Thinking about the traditional pattern of the foundation of associations in the late decades, one will find that they have moved towards becoming dinosaurs vanished because of their inflexibility with the external environment. To adapt to changes, the expansive associations with customary structure should make strides towards a new auxiliary plans and additionally technological advancements (Daft, 1987). Making learning organizations is one method for rebuilding the association toward vitality. A learning organization is one in which learning occurs for persistent change. To encourage this pattern, a learning procedure ought to be in the motivation of the association (Sugerman (2000). Authoritative adapting, at that point, will be a procedure of discovering botches and a shot of recuperating and renewal (Argyris and Schon, 1996)

As Farr (2000) states, organizational learning is a procedure in which organizational learning will be produced. This ought to explicitly happen in such foundations as schools and colleges. Learning, advancement, change, and rivalry ought to thrive in colleges, if not different establishments. Iranian colleges guarantee to be aggressive in the worldwide instruction showcase. Advancing toward learning association may be one of the significant courses toward globalization and aggressiveness. With the start of the 1990s, associations received a rebuilding of their frameworks to have the capacity to contend with the quick changes of innovation, economy,

culture, and governmental issues. Pioneers found that the life of the organization profoundly relies upon learning as a noteworthy instrument to spare and make them powerful. Learning Organization is a kind of organization whose exercises and exhibitions are transformed and recuperated by knowledge and understanding.

Literature Review

Hult et al. (2004) brought up that if a firm is to be imaginative, the executives must devise authoritative highlights that compress a reasonable learning introduction. In particular, some social calculates, for example, decentralized leadership, blunder resistance, or social relations, have appeared to influence information and advanced results through hierarchical learning. Alegre, J. and Chiva, R. (2008) found a positive connection between authoritative learning capacity and advancement in the industry. In their investigation, Organizational Learning Capability was dictated by five fundamental encouraging elements: experimentation, chance-taking, and collaboration with the outer condition, discourse, and participative leadership. Development is imagined as an individual and aggregate learning process that plans to discover better approaches for taking care of issues. Accordingly, advancement appears to rely upon the organization's capacity to learn through which new information is created, circulated, and utilized. Expecting that development and execution in the model taken for the present research require dreams, principles/arranging and arrival of information of college initiative and also the board's respecting of an open framework to speak with outside the college, one may presume that low watched mean of the information on the initial three markers would then prompt advancement and execution.

In a similar examination of the authoritative learning process in Slovenia, Croatia, and Malaysia, Vlado, et al. (2008) found that when obtaining data, Slovenian and Croatian organizations depend more on inward sources (possess representatives, past choices, and so forth.), and casual group meeting while Malaysian organizations will, in general, depend more on outside sources and all the more regularly have workers committed to scanning for outer data, formal leadership, and composed correspondence.

Information securing and information circulation assume essential jobs in authoritative learning. As per Daft and Huber (1987), hierarchical learning happens along with two measurements: the frameworks measurement, which centers on the procurement and dispersion of data, and the interpretive measurement, which includes the elucidation of that data. and comprehension of data by institutional performers are related with information. Ridiculous and Huber saw that the two exercises add to authoritative learning.

Objectives

- To identify effective technology-driven teaching tools to promote active learning for university students.
- To provide a reference guide for future research studies on the university as an learning organization.

TeamLease Skills University –India's First Vocational Skills University- Proved itself as a Learning Organization with Best Practices

About TeamLease Skills University

India's First Vocational Skills University, TeamLease Skills University (TLSU) is located at ITI Tarsali campus at Vadodara and set up under PPP (Public Private Partnership) mode with Department of Labour and Employment, Government of Gujarat. TLSU wants to ensure that they teach what is relevant and what will lead you to getting a better job. TLSU has designed the

6th semester to be on the job training (OJT) to give a detailed practical exposure of the subject rather than just a cursory knowledge of it. As a Skills University, TLSU pray to the one god of employer. The formal and informal sectors of the employed category will be provided skill upgrade options through credential based educational programs and non-credit oriented training programs. Non-formal pedagogy will be deployed for community enrichment programs.

Vision of TLSU

To contribute to the labour market, Society through well-structured and industry-relevant educational programs with employment at the heart of academic offerings, technology at the heart of the operation and academic mobility as the focus deploying inclusive, distributed and low-cost delivery methodology.

Mission of TLSU

To enable all individuals to acquire skills, and capabilities, prepare them to get appropriate employment and ensure their competitiveness in the national and international work environments. TLSU has a PPP with the Government of Gujarat and they are working closely with many industries to ensure that not only our curriculum is in line with what the employer requires but that they can get excellent opportunities for all students to enhance their work career.

Parental Company Team Lease Services

Figure 1 Source: <http://www.teamleaseuniversity.ac.in/parent-company.html>

3 E's of TLSU

TLSU Offerings

Few Tools we use

Bloom’s Taxonomy

TeamLease Skills University always focuses on the learner-centric approach by staying updated with the market changes and filling the gap between academics and industry. Before syllabus designing and getting it approved in the Board of Studies (BOS), academicians firstly understand the requirements from industry and accordingly design the curriculum, so that they can train industry-ready work force. The challenge academics face nowadays are students’ engagement. In TLSU, syllabus and curriculums are designed based on Bloom’s taxonomy.

Bloom identified six levels within the cognitive domain, from the simple recall or recognition of facts, as the lowest level, through increasingly more complex and abstract mental levels, to the highest order which is classified as evaluation.

Learning goals / outcomes are important to establish in a pedagogical interchange so that teachers and students alike understand the purpose of that interchange. Organized objectives help to clarify objectives for themselves and for students. (Training mapped to job Role)

Having an organized set of objectives, helps TLSU faculties to:

- plan and deliver appropriate instruction
- design valid assessment tasks and strategies;
- ensure that instruction and assessment are aligned with the objective

Teaching Tools using Technology

TLSU practices various interesting and technology driven methodologies for students' involvement, participation and overall engagement.

Kahoot for the quiz: Allows trainers to create and manage 'Kahoots' in the form of quizzes, surveys or polls; either asking quick questions 'on the go' to get feedback or opinion, or more in depth questions for formative assessment. Content can be shared with learners and colleagues. Usable on PC, smartphone or tablet.

Quizlet for the quiz: Allows trainers to create and manage quizzes related to the topics they're teaching. The questions can be posed in a number of formats. Usable on PC, smartphone or tablet.

Socrative for the quiz: Allows trainers to create and manage question sets that students complete using tablet devices or smartphones. Quizzes created using PC or Teachers App, students answer questions using Student App.

Mentimeter for the quiz: Pose mentimeter to pose multiple choice questions for students. Each question set has a unique code. Students use //govote.at to give their answers. Trainer uses mentimeter to display responses in class.

Sticky moose for sharing ideas: Allows trainers to create polls, where a question is posed, and possible responses are presented and users vote on their preferred option. Users can also add further options if they prefer. Could be used in class to collect views of students on scenario presented.

Popplet for sharing ideas: Simple mind-mapping tool, often used as iOS app

Pearltrees for sharing ideas: Peartrees is a tool that allows users to create an online collection of web-based resource links, in graphic form, and allows the collection to be shared with 'friends' through social networks.

Thinglink for resources: Can be used to annotate images, with tags. Tags can include text or hyperlinks.

Photostory for resources: Create slideshows using your digital photos. You can touch-up, crop, or rotate pictures. Adding special effects, record, and your own voice to photo stories. Then, personalize them with titles and captions.

Turnitin for resources: Check students' work for potential plagiarism by comparing it against the world's largest comparison data base. Rendering timely feedback to learners and can also save assessment time from trainer's point of view.

Tesresource for resources: TES members can download and share user-generated resources free of charge for all curriculum areas. Patrons need to register.

Edmodo for collaboration: Trainers can post information for their students' just like on Facebook. Learners can be organized into groups. Trainers can give feedback and badges to their learners. The trainers and learners can be linked using Google drive account

TeamUp for collaboration: Team building based on interest area and skill set. Trainers can record progress of teams. Can store teams, randomly generate and have picture for each learner

Answergarden for class activity: Ask question, display answers as word cloud

Managerial Implications & Conclusion

This paper is a guide to many stakeholders like students, academicians and corporate trainers who might be benefited. This can be helpful to government also in context of organizing various workshops and seminars on various technology teaching tools on Train the Trainer (TTT) model. Universities as learning organizations will empower the future of India. We all are living in the era where knowledge, skills and execution of those skills set at right time, at right place are true milestones for the growth of our economy. Being an academicians, we are the makers of India's

future. In true sense, we are for national contribution of skill development. We all know that today's youth instantly Google for small problems soon after any session they attend. It is our accountability to implement certain teaching methodologies which may enhance students' interest as well as engagement. There are so many non-lecture methods to enhance students' interest. Students will not attend session just the purpose of completing their studies, but they will be able to understand the content, will learn new things, will develop skills and then plough back for our dream" Learning organizations- Innovative Trainers- Skilled Youth- Skilled India"

References

1. Alegre, J. & R. Chiva, 2008 assessing the impact of organizational learning capability on product innovation performance: An empirical test. Elsevier/ science direct/ Technovation, 28: 315-326.
2. Anderson, Jodi Lynette, 2006. Exploring institutional change: A case study of one public research university's development of a center for university and community partnerships. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of California, Los Angeles, 295 pages; AAT 3247474
3. Argyris, C. & D. Schon, 1996. Organizational Learning II: Theory, method and practice, Reading, Mass: Addison Wesley.
4. Beodeker, Robert John, 2006. Faculty and student affairs collaboration: Factors that support and inhibit collaborative capacity. Ed.D., Dissertation, Teachers College, Columbia University, AAT 3225117.
5. Chacon, E., 2004. Organizational Learning or Learning Organization: From theory to practice. Unité mixte de recherche CNRS/UT1 Université des Sciences Sociales, Bat. J, 3ème étage Place Anatole France.
6. Chiva, R., J. Alegre, R. Lapiedra, 2007. Measuring organizational learning capability among the workforce. International Journal of Manpower, 28(3): 224-242.
7. Collie, Sarah L., 2002. The learning organization and teaching improvement in academic departments. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Virginia, AAT 3057485.
8. Daft, R.L., and G.P. Huber, 1987. How Organizations Learn: A Communication Framework. Research in the Sociology of Organizations, 5: 1-36. Dettnerman, D.K., 1993. The case for the prosecution: transfer as an epiphenomenon. In D. K.
9. Dettnerman & R. J. Sternberg Eds. Transfer on trial: Intelligence, Cognition, and Instruction. Norwood, NJ: Ablex Publishing Corporation.
10. Dimovski s, Vlado; Skerlavaj, Miha; Kimman, Mok, & Hernaus, Tomislav, 2008. Comparative analysis of the organizational learning process in Slovenia, Croatia, and Malaysia. Expert Systems with Applications, 34: 3063-3070.
11. Farhangi, A.A., 2001. Designing a Model for Implementing Principles of Learning Organization in Iranian Administrative System. Ph.D. Dissertation, Islamic Azad University, Research Branch, Tehran
12. Farr, K., 2000. Organizational learning and knowledge managers. Work Study, 49(1): 14-17.
13. Fiol, C.M. & M.A. Lyles, 1985. Organizational learning. Academy of Management Review, 10 (4): 803-813.
14. Garvin, D.A., 1993. Building a learning organization, Harvard Business Review, 71: 78-91.
15. Hult, G.T.M., R.F. Hurley, G.A. Knight, 2004. Innovativeness: its antecedents and impact on business Performance. Industrial Marketing Management, 33: 429-438.
16. Krejcie, R, & D. Morgan, 1970. Determining sample size for research activities. Educational and Psychological Measurement, (30): 607-610.

17. Motshekga-Sebolai, Motsatsi Elizabeth, 2003. Lifelong learning for the development of academics in institutions of higher learning: With reference to colleges of education and technicians in Gauteng Province Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Pretoria (South Africa), AAT 0805261.
18. Phillips, B.T., 2003. A four level Learning organization benchmark implementation model. *The Learning Organization*, 10: 2.
19. Senge, P.M., 1990. *The fifth discipline*. London: Random House. Senge, P.M., 1994. *The Fifth Discipline: The Art and Practice of the Learning Organization*. New York: Currency Doubleday.
20. Smith, Becky Hampton, 2003. The university as a learning organization: Developing a conceptual model. Ed.D. Dissertation, Montana State University, AAT 3101667.
21. Sugarman, B., 2000. *A learning based approach to leading change*. Lesley University.
22. Weick, K.E. & Leon, 1995. *Creating a Learning Organization: From Theory to Practice*, Human Resource Management, summer.
23. Zally, M. & A. Jafarnejad, 2002. *Measuring the Organizational Learning in Iran's Public Universities*. School of Management, Tehran University, Tehran.